

Assessing the Effectiveness of the Domestic Violence Amendment Act (2021) in Advancing SDG 5.2 in South Africa

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The Domestic Violence Amendment Act (2021) marks an important overhaul of South Africa's legal response to tackle gender-based violence. It aligns with SDG 5.2, which aims to eliminate all violence against women and girls. This study critically assesses the Act's effectiveness by analysing secondary data, including violence statistics, government reports, South African Police Service (SAPS) records, legal documents, and academic research. Using feminist legal and socio-legal theories, the analysis explores how the Act updates legal definitions, strengthens protective measures, and shapes institutional practices. Findings show progress alongside ongoing challenges: the Act broadens the meaning of domestic violence, introduces electronic protection orders, and encourages intersectoral collaboration, yet issues with enforcement, survivor access, and systemic capacity persist. Findings indicate that the Act's provisions align with the target of SDG 5.2. However, the potential of the legislation to improve protection and the legal process hinges on the capacity, disposition, and roles of the various stakeholders. The study concludes that the Act is a good response to violence against women and girls. Still, the impact will be felt more strongly through enhanced multi-sectoral collaboration, commitment, and coordination. Situating the Act in South Africa's socio-legal context and its international commitments, the study recommends comprehensive reforms that incorporate legislative updates, institutional accountability, and community-based initiatives. The research concludes with evidence-based recommendations to support SDG 5.2 and enhance the efficiency of feminist-informed legal frameworks in tackling gender-based violence.

Keywords: Gender-based violence, SDG 5.2, feminist legal theory, socio-legal theory, legislative reform

Violence against Women and Girls (VAWG) is a major scourge that is ravaging many societies around the world. Over the last two decades, globally, nearly one in every three women has suffered physical and/or sexual violence at least once in their life (United Nations Women, 2025). Also, eight percent of women 15 years and older have gone through sexual violence at least once in their life from someone other than a life partner, while 137 women and girls were killed globally by their partners or relatives (UN Women, 2025). Recent studies indicate that in Europe, one out of every 10 women has been a victim of cyber-harassment since age 15 (UN Women Africa, 2025). Across Sub-Saharan Africa, over 1 in every 5 girls and women are victims of rape or sexual assault before turning 18 (United Nations Children Fund, 2024). Also, the United Nations Population Fund (2025:1) reported that “in seven Southern African

countries, about 20 per cent of individuals aged 15 to 24 reported having experienced sexual violence from an intimate partner.” Similarly, a recent report by the Human Sciences Research Council revealed that 35.5 percent of South African women aged 18 and older had experienced lifetime physical and/or sexual violence while 22.4 percent had experienced intimate partner violence (Zungu et al., 2024).

Several efforts have, however, been made at the global and regional levels to fight the violence against women and girls. This led to the introduction of different instruments at the global (e.g. Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Discrimination Against Women [CEDAW], UN Declaration on the Elimination of Violence against Women [DEVAW], Other International Human Rights Treaties [Framework Obligations]) and regional (e.g. Protocol to the African Charter on Human and Peoples' Rights on the Rights of Women in Africa (“Maputo Protocol”), Southern African Development Community [SADC] Protocol on Gender and Development) levels (Deane, 2024).

Meanwhile, VAWG has a longstanding existence in South Africa from the colonial era, and this has largely been reinforced by the apartheid regime. The violence that characterised the fight for freedom during the Apartheid regime appeared to have normalised male (black & white South Africans) violence and aggression. Generally, VAWG includes Gender-Based Violence (GBV), Domestic Violence (DV), Intimate Partner Violence (IPV) and some other forms of violence and abuse. According to the UN Women (2025), 21.3% women in South Africa aged 18 and older have experienced intimate partner physical and/or sexual violence at least once in their lifetime; also, 8.7% has experienced it in the last 12 months. However, in many instances, cases of VAWG go unreported

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and do not get into the official statistics (Vetten, 2014) partly due to fear of shame, stigmatisation and attack (Mutinta, 2022). The resultant effects are more devastating for children, specifically, girls who may be exposed to generational trauma. Today, teenage pregnancy and child-on-child sexual offence are on the rise (Nel, 2025a).

In response to the increasing incidents of VAWG in South Africa, several legislations have been made over the years. These include the Domestic Violence Act 116 of 1998 (amended by Act 14 of 2021), the Criminal Law (Sexual Offences and Related Matters) Amendment Act 32 of 2007, The Protection from Harassment Act 17 of 2011, the Prevention and Combating of Trafficking in Persons Bill 7B of 2010 (adopted 18 March 2013 by the Select Committee on Security & Constitutional Affairs), National Framework on Management of Sexual Offences: Section 62(1) of the Criminal Law (Sexual Offences & Related Matters) Amendment Act, 2007. Unfortunately, these legislations are unable to stem the tide of violence (Bazaanah & Ngcobo, 2024; Wild, 2026).

Following the expiration of the timeline for the Millennium Development Goals, the United Nations introduced the Sustainable Development Goals [SDGs] (2015-2030). Goal 5 seeks to achieve gender equality and empower all women and girls. Specifically, SDG Target 5.2 seeks to eliminate VAWG in public and private spheres by 2030 (World Health Organization, 2025). The implementation of the Domestic Violence Amendment Act (2021) is one of the steps taken by South Africa to achieve the goal. It marks a significant overhaul of South Africa's legal response to combat gender-based violence. The Act became operational on April 14 2023 (South African Legal Information Institute, 2023).

Domestic Violence Amendment Act (2021) defines violence as “physical, sexual, emotional, verbal, psychological, spiritual, economic and elder abuse including intimidation, harassment, stalking, related person abuse, damage to property, coercive and controlling behavior, exposure of a child to domestic violence, and any other behaviour of an intimidating, threatening, abusive, degrading, offensive or humiliating nature towards a complainant, where such conduct harms, or (may cause imminent harm to, the safety, health or well-being of) inspires the reasonable belief that harm may be caused to the complainant” (Republic of South Africa, 2025:6-8).

To implement the Act, certain government departments have been given clear responsibilities. They include the South African Police Service (SAPS), the Department of Justice and Constitutional Development (DOJ & CD), the Department of Health (DoH), the Department of Social Development (DSD), the Department of Communications and Digital Technologies (DCDT) and the Department of Correctional Services (DCS). Others are the Department of Basic Education (DBE), the Department of Higher Education and Training (DHET), and the Department of Finance. The Act provides for the heads of these Departments to hold consultations as may be necessary to guarantee the successful implementation of the law (Republic of South Africa, 2021).

Generally, the Act has become innovative in the areas of definitions and interpretation, obligation of functionaries, obligation to report and give information, entering of private dwellings, domestic violence safety monitoring notice, attendance of witness, electronic communications service providers to furnish information, existing orders/applications, integrated electronic repository,

directives for the clerks of the courts, directives for the departments of health, social development, basic and higher education etc. (National Prosecuting Authority, 2023). Hence, this study critically examines the effectiveness of the Domestic Violence Amendment Act (2021) in advancing SDG 5.2 in South Africa.

In this article, we discuss the prevalence of VAWG around the world, particularly in South Africa. We highlighted the various efforts deployed at the global, regional and national levels. We also examine the strengths and weaknesses of the DVAA and assess its efficiency in achieving SDG 5.2.

Theoretical Framework

The study adopted feminist and socio-legal theories to inform its theoretical understanding. The feminist legal theory developed from the ideas of Elizabeth Cady Stanton in the 19th century (Thomas, 2021) and became prominent in the 1970s. The theory argued that gender inequality is rooted in the unequal treatment of women by the law (Eichner & Huntington, 2016). The proponents believe that certain fundamental stereotypes that underlie the law and legal system are used to perpetuate gender inequality and women's subordination. In other words, they recognize law as a vital agent in women's rights inequality. While challenging the existing nature and structure of the law, they advocate changing it to achieve formal equality.

Though the theory has been criticised for overemphasising victimisation and relying on subjective narratives, in relation to this study, it helps understand that the law is one of the instruments that create an enabling environment for VAWG to thrive and endure. For instance, the theorists argue that the law is designed to sustain and rationalise the 'unfair' and 'unequal' socio-cultural practices that tend to subdue the female gender. Also, the amendment of the law in the fight against VAWG should extend beyond the GBV laws (the Criminal and Related Matters Amendment Act 12 of 2021, the Criminal Law (Sexual Offences & Related Matters) Amendment Act 13 of 2021, and the Domestic Violence Amendment Act 14 of 2021). The family law, labour law, electoral law, etc., may be amended to enhance the socio-economic and political status of women and girls in society.

In addition, socio-legal theory examines the link between law and society. The basic assumptions of the theory originated from the ideas of Emile Durkheim and Max Weber. It looks at how law influences social behaviour and how social forces (such as patriarchy, culture, race & historical inequality) shape legal norms and social institutions, including power relations. As such, “law is seen as a set of socially institutionalised norms of varying degrees of formality, ranging from statutes and judicial decisions at the formal end of the spectrum to socially institutionalised norms and cultural understandings that become embedded in everyday life at the informal end of the spectrum” (Edelman & Galanter, 2015:604). The theorists see law as an instrument of women's domination and gender inequality. It emphasizes how social norms and patriarchal structures limit the effectiveness of legal protections (Bermúdez et al., 2023). In application to this study, the theory argues that patriarchal views and ideas underlie the laws and they are framed in ways that violence against women and girls and are perpetually sustained. Critics contend that the theory lacks clear normative standards and undermines legal certainty (Cotterrell, 2023). However, it helps to explain how law is rooted within complex

socio-cultural constructions. In essence, the two theories challenge legal neutrality, emphasising that laws are not value-free and are built to endorse patriarchal order. Basically, feminist legal theory examines the extent to which the DVAA prioritises the interests of the female gender over patriarchal norms and structures, while socio-legal theory assesses the 'gains' of the Act in terms of implementation.

Method

This study adopts a critical narrative design to analyse secondary data on the Domestic Violence Amendment Act (2021) and VAWG. This method was adopted because it allows for a careful analysis of how legal reforms are framed, implemented and experienced within the South African context, and how these align with the targets of SDG 5.2. It also enables an interpretive and theory-driven analysis of relevant legal documents, government and parliamentary reports, violence statistics, SAPS records, and peer-reviewed academic literature. Doctrinal analysis was used to analyse legal texts, and other data were subjected to thematic analysis.

Exploring the Effectiveness of the DVAA (2021)

Extended Legal Definitions

The expansion of legal definitions of domestic violence in the DVAA reflects improved victim protection. Sexual harassment, related person abuse, spiritual abuse, elder abuse, coercive behavior, exposure of a child to domestic violence have been included in an attempt to cover other forms of abuse that were not clearly addressed. The inclusion of spiritual abuse indicates socio-religious consideration in the amended law. The definition of weapon covers any object that can cause dangerous bodily harm (Calvino & Matadi, 2023). Specifically, the definition of close relationship was included in the amendment. This helps to clarify the relationship between the perpetrator and the victim, and it has implications for justice. There are 24 definitions in the old Act while the new Act has 52 definitions (Moolla, 2023). This will help the criminal justice system in putting each case into context towards aiding investigation and judgment.

However, certain gaps have been identified in the definitions and interpretation of the DVAA. Singo (2023a) noted that some of the definitions are not adequately operationalised and are therefore ambiguous. He argued that cases involving non-physical abuse (e.g. psychological, emotional, and economic abuse) may be difficult to prove because the law does not give enough clarity about it. For instance, Artz and Smythe (2005) argued that the DVA 1998 failed to fully recognise the negative financial hardships experienced by victims of economic abuse. Though, educational expenses has been added to the definition in the amended Act, the gap identified is yet to be filled. Meanwhile, economic abuse is still high in the country as over one in every 10 women experience it (Zungu et al., 2024).

Also, the Act covers the vulnerability of children to domestic violence, but makes no provision to protect them from the indirect impact of the violence (Asamaowei, 2024). In other words, the Act views the exposure of a child to violence as domestic violence but fails to recognise exposure of a child to domestic violence as child abuse or emotional abuse. According to Asamaowei (2024:21), children “may be indirectly affected by the violence witnessed in their homes either by seeing or hearing it take place or by merely being aware without seeing or hearing”. As such, “both parents, from the provision could be said to expose the child to domestic violence:

the perpetrator parent who commits the act of domestic violence; and the victim parent, who remains” (Ngcingane, 2025:52). Meanwhile, “the victim parent sometimes only considers the matter serious enough to leave, if the child is a direct victim of abuse” (Ngcingane, 2025:40). Therefore, there is a need for legal clarity to protect the victim parent, and ensure that the child does not lose both parents into criminality or exposed to further abuse.

Protective measures for Victims and Survivors

The Act has made some contributions towards ensuring better protection for victims of VAWG. It clarifies that persons such as counsellors, health service providers, members of the SAPS, social workers, or teachers have a legal responsibility to apply for a protection order on behalf of victims (Section 4). This helps to ensure that the victim has the necessary protection against possible harm by the alleged perpetrator, even when they are vulnerable and unable to apply for protection personally.

The provision of the amended law enabling the lodging of application for protection order either physically with the clerk of the court or electronically through a designated virtual platform makes it easy for victims to seek protection using the most convenient option, especially for those who may want to conceal their plans from their abusers. This initiative also allows Non-Governmental Organisations (NGOs) to assist victims in lodging applications. More importantly, an electronic application tends to ensure that the relevant government functionaries act on it promptly, since the date and time of submission cannot be tampered with. For instance, the court now has a roster of clerks available to attend to cases that arise outside working hours and days (Moolla, 2023). This roster is shared with the local SAPS station and on the DOJ & CD website for easy access.

In addition, for ease of reference and administrative purposes, the Act mandates that the court clerk maintain an integrated electronic repository or database of all applications and approved protection orders. Also, the provisions of Section 5 of the Act address any abuse committed using technology, thereby providing cover for victims of cyberbullying, cyber stalking and other forms of abuse that take place online. Abuses through online platforms have serious negative consequences for the victim's mental health and general well-being (Khanyile & Ngema, 2025) and this is rife in South Africa. Therefore, the expansion has the potential to increase reporting of VAWG cases and access to justice, as well as deter many people from committing the act.

Further, the introduction of the domestic violence safety monitoring notice requires the court to grant prompt attention to cases of VAWG (Section 4A). It also provides a framework for substantial protection of the complainant, including regular visits by a designated SAPS officer serving the area where the complainant resides (Republic of South Africa, 2021:26). These are targeted towards a fast-track proceeding and improved protection for the complainant. Further, Section 5A appears to guarantee a thorough investigation into fairness and justice by declaring a failure by any person to respond to a subpoena an offence (Republic of South Africa, 2021:32). This tends to eliminate flimsy excuses that are often used to frustrate proceedings and delay justice.

Additionally, the Act notes that once a protection order is issued, the clerk must ensure that it is served on the respondent within 48 hours (Section 6). However, for timeliness, the DOJ and CD has directed that the service must be made within 24 hours (Kubayi,

2025). Amendments to Section 9 clarify that following a court order, a weapon in possession of a respondent must be seized even if they are acquired in an official capacity. As a stern deterrence, the Act further indicates that anyone who contravenes certain provisions in sections 7, 8 and 11, is liable on conviction and may suffer imprisonment for up to 10 years. Also, due to the high level of poverty in the land, and to ensure that justice prevails. Section 19 provides financial protection to the complainant, respondent and witness in cases of domestic violence (Republic of South Africa, 2021:60). According to the DOJ and CD (2025a), victims receive full support at every stage. in pursuit of justice. Victims may benefit from monetary support and counselling services.

Some of the efforts made post-implementation of the DVAA include the establishment of 40 additional GBVF-related offences courts, upgrading of 40 existing courts, increasing of Thuthuzela Care Centres [TCCs] to 66 (Kubayi, 2025). This is in addition to strengthened sexual offence register and improved support services for vulnerable persons (Ramaphosa, 2025). Apart from improved intermediary services, 311 courts were upgraded to become disability-centric; private testimony options, private waiting rooms, emotional containment services, sign language and materials in Braille and audio formats were also introduced (DOJ & CD, 2025a). Further, organisations with vulnerable persons in their employments are now required by law to vet employees against the NRSO [National Register for Sexual Offenders] (DOJ & CD, 2025a). This is to ensure that they are not exposed to convicted sex offenders.

There are reports that following the introduction of the DVAA, the SAPS has improved in terms of its GBVF operations and case management. This includes a GBV Information Centre, victim-friendly facilities and services, and the setting up of GBV desks in all their stations countrywide (Ramaphosa, 2025). Generally, the SAPS GBVF action plan includes: compliance with existing and new regulations; improved investigation and internal regulatory framework; training and sensitisation; enhanced monitoring, coordination and reporting; improved complaint management systems, functional GBV desks, and victim-friendly facilities; support for evidence-based research (SAPS, 2025). The action plan is expected to lead to a significant improvement in the fight against VAWG.

The above are some of the efforts of the government to stem the tide of VAWG in South Africa. However, Asamaoewei (2024) noted that most of the victims of GBV lack confidence in the SAPS and regard their conduct as unprofessional, and this may significantly impact the likelihood of seeking help. For instance, some officers tell victims to resolve their matter privately because 'it is a family matter' (Amnesty International, 2025). A recent study by van Niekerk (2024) on the SAPS in Johannesburg revealed several weaknesses in operational standards that negatively affected the fight against VAWG. The risk of this bad conduct is that the situation may worsen for the victims. This is because "women who have experienced violence are more likely to suffer from depression, anxiety disorders, unplanned pregnancies, sexually transmitted infections, and HIV, with long-lasting consequences" (UN Women, 2025:1). Meanwhile, the police have the primary role of ensuring that the victims are well protected.

The non-criminalisation of domestic violence by the Act (though Section 17 shows how violation of certain provisions of the DVAA, such as a protection order, may result in crime) places so many duties on the SAPS to ensure protection. However, the DVAA has led to an

amendment of the criminal law (Criminal & Related Matters Amendment Act No. 12 of 2021), which now provides for a more stringent penalty for perpetrators. The South African Law Reform Commission [SALRC] (2023) argued that the enactment is inadequate to remedy the harms of domestic violence; hence, it may lead to unintended consequences. Concerns around sentencing may deter reporting and lead to undue endurance on the part of the victim until the situation turns awry. This is especially true when the perpetrator appears to be the family's breadwinner; a new set of victims may emerge. Alternatively, the Commission opined that sentencing should be informed by the impact of the violence on the victim. While the submission of the SALRC appears considerable, it may turn out to partly sustain the perpetuation of domestic violence.

DVAA and Renewed Institutional Practices: A Glimpse

The Act enhances coordination between legal, social, and health services, facilitating a victim-centred approach. The Act gives the SAPS additional responsibilities, which require increased funding for the Service and regular training for its personnel (Singo, 2023b). The Act also provides a clear mandate for the Director-General of Communications and Digital Technologies to ensure that electronic communications service providers make all necessary information available to assist courts in domestic violence cases. In particular, the Department of Justice and Constitutional Development (DOJ & CD) issued Regulations to facilitate the easy understanding and application of the DVAA. For instance, the Department identified 42 forms relevant to the Act (DOJ & CD, 2022).

Though the DVAA has been widely commended, the implementation of the Act is plagued with systemic barriers that impede justice for survivors (Nel, 2025b). Section 18 of the DVAA provides for collaboration among various departments of government against domestic violence. This goes in line with the National Strategic Plan on Gender-Based Violence and Femicide (NSP-GBVF) especially, Pillar 3, which focuses on Justice, Safety and Protection. Recently, the Department of Women, Youth and Persons with Disabilities (2025) reported that from 2023/2024 financial year, only 16 out of 40 departments of government were in the range of 80% and above regarding compliance with reporting implementation progress on NSP-GBVF. This suggests that even at that national level of leadership, there is inadequate coordination and commitment to the fight against GBVF. It therefore becomes worrisome to assess the level of success that can be achieved through the DVAA, especially given the classification of GBV as a national disaster in November 2025.

The current provision of the Act, channeling all VAWG cases through the judicial process, places a heavy workload on the court (Wisenberg, 2025) and the SAPS, given current manpower constraints. However, it did not pay specific attention to address the procedural delays and administrative bottleneck (such as delayed court resolution) being faced by police officers and court officials that often affect the victims of GBV (South Africa Law Reform Commission, 2023). This has a serious negative implication for victims and survivors, as they must endure the delays in legal proceedings.

According to Wisenberg (2025:1), "early observations reveal inconsistent implementation across different courts. Some magistrates conduct extensive inquiries with witness testimony, while others handle the process more summarily". This creates a potential risk to the fairness and justice of the victims. The

Commission, however, cautioned that criminalising the failure of police officers to properly discharge their duties relating to GBV may result in unintended consequences and constitute higher risks for victims. Rather, it suggests adopting disciplinary actions, training, and retraining, and monitoring and evaluation. Moreover, there are instances in which ineffectiveness is associated with a lack of skills, expertise, or competence (Mofokeng et al., 2023).

Recently, a government official confirmed that the police were not working at the speed needed for justice (Dlabathi, 2026). Examples include a DNA backlog exceeding 140,000 cases (RSA Parliament, 2025) and a toxicology backlog exceeding 40,000 cases in 2025 (Ruiters, 2025). This is partly due to the shortage of relevant health professionals and facilities. For instance, there are only two permanent forensic nurses in the whole of the Western Cape (Amnesty International, 2025), and the TCCs are poorly funded nationwide, thereby hampering campaign and other activities (Mnyakeni, 2023). These challenges may lead to other forms of crime as victims or affected people may take the law into their hands in a bid to avenge or protect themselves due to the 'long distance to justice'. It also undermines justice when cases are dismissed for lack of evidence. Importantly, it suggests some level of inefficiency and inadequate commitment to the DVAA within the SAPS and the criminal justice system at large.

Also, it is expected that, pursuant to the amendment Act, the government will carry out significant recruitment in the SAPS to effectively implement the law's provisions. Recently, the leadership of the Service lamented that it is quite challenging to ensure police monitoring of victims' safety after a court issues a protection order, due to inadequate manpower (SAPS, 2025). While the law's provision is commendable, implementation is indeed an issue. Also, the requirement for police to collect protection orders daily from the courts and ensure service on the suspects further places the SAPS under pressure due to staff shortages. As such, the SAPS is requesting to work 'as soon as possible' (for genuine constraints) and to also facilitate the electronic transmission of protection orders to police stations (SAPS, 2025). This therefore suggests that there is inadequate consultation among relevant stakeholders, especially SAPS, during the amendment of the Act.

Attaining SDG 5.2 in South Africa: Looking Beyond the DVAA

Beyond the DVAA and other legislations, National Strategic Plan on Gender-Based Violence and Femicide (NSP-GBVF), National Council on Gender-Based Violence and Femicide Act (2024) GBVF Acceleration Action Plan (2025) "No More Violence" manual (to enlighten service providers and victims on acceptable standard of operation), annual Victims' Rights Week (to inform the general public on the rights of victims & the various options available to them) amongst others are part of the measures deployed towards tackling VAWG.

The introduction of the DVAA of 2021 is seen as a significant step towards addressing VAWG; however, it has not been easy to reverse its increasing trend, as the crime persists. Unfortunately, the consequences are grievous. Essentially, it is impossible to have a perfect law; hence, the reason for amendments to fill gaps and improve existing laws in the interest of the people. Similarly, the DVAA is not a perfect Act, but it has significantly improved legislation against domestic violence. Meanwhile, according to Thorpe (2013), legislation and policies cannot be used to tackle

VAWG in isolation. Moreover, they seem poorly implemented, especially in service delivery to victims. A review of the Act's performance after about 3 years of implementation suggests a need for greater efforts beyond the DVAA.

According to Nel (2025b:1), "Too many women live in fear, too many children carry the scars of violence, and too many families mourn lives stolen by brutality". The intent of the Act is clear, but South Africa appears to be a nation where strong laws exist but are poorly enforced (Stone, 2022) culminating in the ineffectiveness of the DVAA. This indeed has implications for the protection of survivors and accountability of perpetrators (Malambe & Kumalo, 2025) if there are no concerted efforts among the various stakeholders to fight the scourge (Women For Change, 2025).

Indeed, addressing VAWG requires more proactive rather than reactive efforts. The current approach in South Africa places more emphasis on response to VAWG. The National Prosecuting Authority reported that conviction rates for Femicide cases between 2021 and 2024 exceeded 90% annually (Nel, 2025b). Also, between January 1 and April 9, 2025, 86.9% (574) and 78.7% (1,061) sexual offence cases were finalised with verdicts in the Free State and the Eastern Cape, respectively (Nel, 2025c). The statistics are impressive, but they did not lead to a reduction in GBVF incidents in the country. During the 2024/2025 financial year, more than one million new protection order applications were received (DOJ & CD, 2025b). This is enormous and indicates a need for an intervention beyond legislative amendments. Moreover, it is practically impossible to convict everyone in the country.

Recently, after observing the situation following the implementation of the DVAA for about 3 years, President Cyril Ramaphosa expressed concern that South Africa has one of the highest levels of GBVF globally, leading to it being classified as a national disaster (Ramaphosa, 2025). This shows that the DVAA may not meet the requirements of SDG Target 5.2 by 2030. It appears that the ineffectiveness of the Act and the criminal justice system is rooted in the socio-historical and cultural fabric (religion, education, tradition, etc.) of the country (South Africa Law Reform Commission, 2023). The danger of this reality is that the understanding of the various functionaries that are legally saddled with the responsibility of fighting GBV seems not to be largely different from the mentality of perpetrators that are meant to be brought to book. Hence, achieving meaningful results becomes difficult, and many victims tend not to report potential cases.

Meanwhile, it is important to note that some of the challenges to an effective fight against GBV stem from certain mindsets and the structure of society. For example, a long distance to the police station or court may reduce the likelihood of reporting or of eventual access to justice (SALRC, 2023) for a victim of GBV due to concerns about costs, time, and secondary victimisation. According to the SALRC (2023:12), "socio-economic factors seem to underpin not only the prevalence of domestic violence but redress thereof. It recognises too that the multi-varied interplay of socioeconomic, normative and relational complexities often makes the law an ineffective tool to address these complexities". Beyond the patriarchal nature of South Africa, some other factors such as alcohol and substance abuse, access to firearms, structural, societal and normative barriers (SALRC, 2023), socio-economic challenges, government deficits and marginalisation (Centre for the Study of Violence & Reconciliation, 2025a) have been identified as predictors of domestic violence.

According to Armstrong (1994:37), “systemic oppression, state-sponsored violence, and the militarisation of society in apartheid era South Africa bred a culture of aggression in which both black and white cultures intensified their male-dominated power-systems and thus normalised, tolerated and encouraged male violence and aggression”. While it is arguable that domestic violence precedes apartheid, it further entrenches the undue dominance of women and girls and is discreetly woven into the legal and social fabrics of South Africa. Put differently, it shapes the nature of women's struggles (Bazanaah, 2024). GBV is an offshoot of the socio-economic inequality that has characterised the country for many decades.

For instance, the police, one of the agencies of government in the fight against VAWG had 417 of its officers reported for domestic violence between 2021 and 2022 (Lopes, 2025). The rate increased in 2024, with 237 officers reported between April and September (SAPS, 2024). These raise concerns about trust and safety within communities, especially regarding the possibility of pursuing justice within the perpetrator's sphere of influence and power. “Moreover, when police officers cover up or ignore domestic violence within their ranks or actively prevent victims from getting the help they need, they become as complicit as the perpetrators of that violence (Lopes, 2025:2)”. Also, a recent report alleged that an official of the Justice Department in Mpumalanga poured boiling water on his wife for declining to cook due to tiredness; months after the incident was reported, the suspect was yet to be arraigned (Hlatshwayo, 2026) perhaps, with the exploitation of some lacunas in the law.

Again, the amendments to the DVA are highly commendable, but the targeted results may not be achieved if fundamental issues of overbearing patriarchy and inequality are not addressed (Asamaoewei, 2024). It may be difficult to achieve a reform through law if it clashes with the beliefs of the 'significant majority' (Asamaoewei, 2024). These are partly the reasons for the lingering high rate of GBV. Amnesty International (2025) noted that there was an average of 116 reported cases of rape and 20 sexual assaults per day in 2024 in South Africa. There were also 5,578 and 7,239 murder and attempted murder incidents, respectively, among women in the same year (Amnesty International, 2025). Hence, the National Prosecuting Authority (2023) noted a need for change at different levels individual, relationship, children, family, community, society. While arguing for the protection of children, it also suggested that mediation may be necessary to address domestic issues within families, as litigation can take time and have untold consequences for the children involved.

In addition, the SAPS challenged over-reliance on criminal law as a response to domestic violence, arguing that “a preventative lens in which normative change is brought about in society would bear better results” (SALRC, 2023:138). Centre for the Study of Violence and Reconciliation (CSV) (2025b:3) suggests seeking solutions through “access to justice, education systems, overcoming funding gaps, technology and digital tools, and men as partners in prevention”.

Recently, the President of South Africa acknowledged that, despite various efforts (including the National Strategic Plan on GBV), implementation remains uneven (Ramaphosa, 2025). This indicates a need for significant improvement in coordination and collaboration among the various stakeholders. However, government policies are not supposed to be fragmented; they must be systematically linked to a central plan. For instance, the current plan to grant recognition to sex work (DOJ & CD, 2025b)

ideologically translates to the commodification of sex, which may partly expose the female gender to sexual exploitation and violence. In other words, it has the tendency to undermine the relative gains against GBV in South Africa.

Essentially, it is high time South Africa moved away from carceral feminism (a hegemonic approach to addressing GBV largely premised on the use of the criminal justice system). This approach commits the government only to improve spending on reactive efforts through the police, courts, and prisons, at the expense of the provision of social services that empower women (Breton, 2023) and girls. For 2025 only, R57.2 billion was budgeted for GBV, and more than half (58.7%) was already spent before mid-year [as of May] (Department of Women, Youth & Persons with Disabilities, 2025). Regrettably, these funds would have improved the well-being of women and girls if they were directed to social services.

In view of this, there is a need for a total overhaul of the South African socio-economic structure to identify the elements and factors that motivate GBV, and to infuse systemic and progressive changes targeted at eliminating GBV. Put differently, a gradual but systemic change in certain aspects of the people's socio-cultural beliefs and values will help give the needed respect and recognition to every gender or sex. There is also a need for society-wide aggressive and time-to-time sensitisation and orientation programmes (through the media) and in communities to sensitise people against GBV (Nanthambwe & Magezi, 2024) including education of women and girls about the DVAA in the event of violence. This is because many people are not familiar with the legal provision. In other words, it is imperative to embark on transformative societal reform beyond legal reform, given the financial cost to the nation.

This is after an evidence-based understanding of the psychology that underlie domestic violence (Furusa & Limberg, 2015). Also, the educational curriculum across all levels is to be refined to include lessons that can help to reduce violence, especially against women and girls. This is more important currently, when children are increasingly becoming perpetrators of violence (Nel, 2025c). Hence, there is a need to conscientiously address the pandemic and hold perpetrators to account, dismantle unfair patriarchal norms and rape culture that is brewing violence in society. This requires behavioural change and commitment of departments and agencies of governments, as well as non-governmental organisations. This is to ensure that the current challenges of coordination gaps, underfunding, and limited implementation capacity (DWYPD, 2025) are eliminated effectively.

Conclusion

The Domestic Violence Amendment Act was implemented to tackle domestic violence, including violence against women and girls. In theory, the law has recorded considerable progress, but in practice, there are indications of inefficiency and gaps. Some legal definitions are ambiguous and need clarification. The law introduced enhanced protective measures for victims or survivors of violence, but this places enormous responsibility on the criminal justice system, especially the SAPS. Though the law has led to the implementation of some policies, unfortunately, there is inadequate commitment and collaboration among the various stakeholders, thereby negatively impacting the fight against GBV in South Africa. Essentially, to achieve SDG 5.2, society needs to undergo a broad restructuring to address the scourge. This includes mindset and behavioural change

among people in various sectors of society to effectively reduce violence against women and girls to a bearable minimum.

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